
Exploring The Relationship Between Spiritual Attitude And Cognitive Emotion Regulation among Adults: A Gender Based Analysis

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Abstract:

The present study looks at the relationship between spiritual attitudes and cognitive emotion regulation strategies among adults with a emphasis on gender differences. A cluster sampling strategy was used to pick 200 participants (100 males and 100 females) from the Varanasi district of Uttar Pradesh between the ages of 18 to 25. Two standardized tools were used: the Spiritual Involvement and Beliefs Scale (SIBS) and the Cognitive Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (CERQ). The findings demonstrated that females had a greater spiritual attitude than males but there was no significant gender difference in the use of cognitive emotion regulation mechanisms. Spiritual attitude and cognitive emotion regulation were found moderately positively correlated, suggesting that those who have higher spiritual beliefs also tend to use more adaptive cognitive techniques to control their emotions. The results emphasise the need of integrating spiritual awareness into mental health and educational programs for young adults and imply that spirituality plays a significant role in emotional regulation. These findings have ramifications for educators, counsellors, and legislators who seek to advance emotional health via all-encompassing strategies.

Keywords: *Spiritual Attitude, Cognitive Emotion Regulation, Adults*

Introduction:

Adolescent is age group who experience rapid change in their emotional state, in this age they are prone to emotional flood, they experience sudden change in the emotion, in this regard spirituality is one of the key components which play a very significant relationship in emotional regulation, and also helps to cope in the adverse situation. Spirituality is "that part of the psyche that strives for transcendental values, meaning, and experience" and deals with "the search for

meaning and purpose in life." (Ellis, 1999). A person's attitude is their inclination to react either positively or negatively to a thing, someone, an organisation, an occasion, or any discriminatory element of their environment. Ajzen. 1989. It should be underlined that the following should be included in the process of forming students' moral and spiritual attitudes at this point in society's development: the educational and educational resources of the moral and spiritual culture of society;

the potential of the higher education institution's educational and sociocultural environment; and the spiritual self-realization of the student's personality, self-improvement, and spiritual self-development (Shavkatovna, 2021). Emotion regulation is assumed to be an important factor in determining well-being and/or successful functioning (Cicchetti et al., 1995, Thompson, 1991). The general concept of emotion regulation can be understood as “all the extrinsic and intrinsic processes responsible for monitoring, evaluating and modifying emotional reactions, especially their intensive and temporal features, to accomplish one's goals” (Thompson, 1994, p. 27). According to this definition, the concept of emotion regulation is a very broad conceptual rubric encompassing many regulatory processes, such as the regulation of emotions by oneself versus the regulation of emotions by others and the regulation of the emotion itself versus the regulation of its underlying features (Thompson & Calkins, 1996). Therefore, a broad spectrum of biological, social, behavioural, and conscious and unconscious cognitive processes can be referred to as emotion regulation. Coping is a process that unfolds in the context of a situation or condition that is appraised as personally significant and as taxing or exceeding the individual's resources for coping (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). It is a complicated, multifaceted process that is sensitive both to environment, its needs and resources, and to personality traits. Monat & Lazarus 1991, Offer a definition that refers to coping as the „individual's

efforts to master demands (conditions of pain, threat, challenge) that are judged (or perceived) as exceeding or draining one's resources.

Review of Literature:

Abundant of research suggests that spiritual attitude has an important role in cognitive emotion control methods for dealing with adversity. (Firooz. et al. 2017) discovered that spiritual attitude is one of the components of psychology that play an important part in emotion regulation.

Their study aims to assess the role of spiritual orientation in predicting cognitive-emotional control techniques among Tabriz University of Medical Sciences students in Tabriz, Iran. Spiritual attitude may have a crucial role in developing more efficient cognitive emotion regulation mechanisms, and students with a stronger spiritual attitude were able to regulate their emotions more successfully. In the summer of 2020, Safara et al. investigated the influence of emotion management and spirituality in predicting the psychological well-being of the elderly in Qazvin, Iran.

The findings revealed a direct and significant relationship between psychological well-being and emotion regulation, specifically reappraisal and suppression. Furthermore, psychological well-being demonstrated a direct and significant association with spirituality and its components, such as spiritual attitude and spiritual ability.

According to the results of the standardised regression coefficient (Beta),

emotion regulation components such as reappraisal and suppression, as well as spirituality components such as spiritual attitude and spiritual ability, can positively predict the psychological well-being of seniors. According to the findings of this study, improving emotion regulation traits and providing grounds for spirituality in elders can increase their psychological well-being. Heydari-Viyari, S., and Yousefi, M. 2022 sought to forecast the dimensions of mental health based on spiritual health and emotion management strategies during the coronavirus pandemic in Iran.

The findings revealed that spiritual health, adaptive, and maladaptive emotion regulation mechanisms predict 34%, 19%, and 43% of mental health changes, respectively. According to the findings, it is necessary to focus on the spiritual dimension while simultaneously teaching the application of proper emotion regulation skills in stressful situations in order to promote the mental health of various members of society. Dehghanizadeh, , et al., and Eydi-Baygi, M. 2021 conducted a study on the Prediction of Health Anxiety Based on Spiritual Well-being and Cognitive Emotion Regulation Strategies during COVID-19 in Iranian Individuals.

The findings revealed that health anxiety had a significant detrimental impact on spiritual well-being and adaptive cognitive emotion regulation techniques. Furthermore, health anxiety revealed a substantial positive connection with maladaptive cognitive emotion control techniques. The findings of the *Piyush Kumar Tripathy, Rajesh Kumar Srivastava & Anant Shankar Pandey*

study revealed the effects of spiritual well-being and cognitive emotion control methods on health anxiety. As a result, it is suggested that training based on spiritual teachings and emotion regulation strategies reduce health anxiety during the COVID-19 outbreak.

Akbari and Hossaini (2018) investigated how emotional regulation mediates the relationship between spiritual health, quality of life, psychological health, and burnout. The hierarchical regression analysis revealed that emotional regulation has a relative mediating function in the association between spiritual health and quality of life, as well as a complete mediating role in the relationship between spiritual health, mental health, and burnout.

They discovered a complex and non-linear relationship between spiritual health and quality of life, as well as mental health and burnout. This association may be altered by emotional regulation. Miri et al. (2021). Their study sought to propose a causal model of emotional regulation based on a system of beliefs and spiritual intelligence mediated by areas of concern among Tehran students. The findings revealed that the system of beliefs and spiritual intelligence, together with the mediation of areas of concern, had an impact on emotion regulation in Tehran students (Ghazipoor, et al., 2021).

They conducted research to look into the mediating function of resilience in the relationship between emotional control, spirituality, and death anxiety in cancer patients. The findings demonstrated that cognitive modulation of emotion,

spirituality, and resilience has a strong direct effect on death anxiety. Furthermore, cognitive modulation of emotion and spirituality has a substantial impact on resilience. Furthermore, resilience has a major impact on death dread through indirect cognitive modulation of emotion and spirituality. The findings of this study highlight the importance of personality and spiritual aspects in the psychological problems of cancer patients, with implications for psychotherapy.

Rationale of the Study:

In present time various news and incident have been reported, regarding misconduct, criminal activity and antisocial and notorious activity and other psychological issues in which adolescents are directly or indirectly related with such incidents. There is various study have conducted in abroad to uncover its major factor which also has been mention in the above literature review that how spiritual attitude significantly affect cognitive emotion regulation strategies to deal with adverse situation and created major psychological issues, but few studies have been conducted in Indian context that can uncover major issues in regarding emotion regulation in terms of adolescents.

Objective of the Study:

On the basis of literature & obtained relevant gap, the following objective has been formulated for the proposed research study.

1. To examine the relationship between spiritual attitude and

cognitive emotion regulation in adults.

2. To assess gender differences in spiritual attitude and cognitive emotion regulation strategies.

Hypotheses of the Study:

Hypothesis-Based on the above objective the following hypothesis have been formulated:

1. There is a significant relationship between spiritual attitude and cognitive emotion regulation strategies in adults.
2. There is a significant gender difference in spiritual attitudes and cognitive emotion regulation strategies.

Methodology:

Participant:

The sample size is 200. The participant is 100 male and 100 female of age group of 18 to 25 year. The cluster sample technique has been used to select the participant from Varanasi district of Uttar Pradesh (India).

Instruments:

The **Spiritual Involvement and Beliefs Scale (SIBS)** by Hatch et al. (1998) is a **26-item tool** that assesses spirituality across four areas: *Personal Application, Spiritual Activities, Religious Support, and Existential Well-being*. It uses **5-point Likert's scale** with higher scores indicating greater spirituality. The SIBS shows **high reliability ($\alpha = 0.92$)** and **good validity** suitable for both clinical and research use.

The **Cognitive Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (CERQ)** by Goreskiet al. (2001) is a **36-item self-report scale** that measures how people cognitively cope with negative events. It includes **nine subscales** such as Self-Blame, Acceptance, Rumination, and Positive Reappraisal. Responses are rated on a **5-point Likert's scale**, and scores are averaged per subscale. The CERQ has **good reliability ($\alpha = 0.68-0.86$)** and **validity**, making it useful for research on stress, anxiety, and depression.

Research Design:

A descriptive correlation design was employed.

Statistical Analysis:

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic and variable-related data. Pearson's correlation coefficient was employed to examine the relationship between spiritual attitude and

cognitive emotion regulation strategies as well as an independent samples t-test was used to assess gender differences in both spiritual attitude and cognitive emotion regulation.

Results:

Table 1 shows the mean scores for spiritual attitude among male and female participants. The findings indicate that females ($M = 75.86$, $SD = 10.463$) have a higher mean spiritual attitude score than males ($M = 69.54$, $SD = 9.208$). This suggests that female participants have a higher spiritual propensity or belief system than their male counterparts. The significant mean difference implies a gender-based variation in spiritual attitude, indicating that females may rely more on spirituality in their daily lives or during emotional situations.

Table1: Mean difference of Spiritual Attitude

Gender	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Male	69.54	9.208	100
Female	75.86	10.463	100

Figure 1 depicts the mean difference in spiritual attitudes between male and female participants. The graph plainly shows that girls have significantly higher mean scores than males. This

picture confirms the numerical findings in Table 1, indicating that female participants have a higher level of spiritual belief or participation.

Figure 1: Mean Analysis

Table 2 shows the mean scores for cognitive emotion management techniques among men and women. The findings show that females (M = 89.12, SD = 5.769) scored somewhat higher than males (M = 88.39, SD = 5.944). However, the

difference is negligible, implying that both genders use cognitive emotion management methods at roughly equal degrees. This suggests that gender does not play a significant effect in the overall use of cognitive coping techniques.

Table 2: Mean difference of Cognitive Emotion Regulation strategy

Gender	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Male	88.39	5.944	100
Female	89.12	5.769	100

Figure 2 illustrates an average examination of cognitive emotion management strategies for both genders. Females had slightly greater bar heights

than males, which supports Table 2's findings. However, the picture emphasises that the difference is minor and most likely not statistically significant.

Figure 2: Mean Analysis

Table 3 shows the Pearson correlation coefficient for spiritual attitudes and cognitive emotion management techniques. The correlation coefficient ($r = 0.495$) is modest and statistically significant ($p = 0.048$), implying a favourable association between

the two variables. This shows that people with greater spiritual views are more likely to adopt successful cognitive emotion management mechanisms. The importance of this link lends credence to the concept that spirituality favourably influences emotional regulating systems.

Table 3: Relationship between Spiritual Attitude and Cognitive Emotion Regulation strategy

Name of the Variables		Spiritual Attitude	Cognitive Emotion Regulation strategy
Spiritual Attitude	Pearson correlation	1	.495
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.048
	N	200	200
Cognitive Emotion Regulation strategy	Pearson correlation	.495	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.048	
	N	200	200

The findings of the independent samples t-test for both variables are shown in Table 4. With a significance level of $p = .000$ and a t-value of -4.534 for spiritual attitude, there is a significant difference between males and females, with females scoring higher. The t-value for the

cognitive emotion control approach, on the other hand, is -0.881 with $p = .379$, indicating that there is no discernible gender difference. This demonstrates that although gender influences spiritual attitude, it has no effect on people's ability to rationally control their emotions.

Table 4: Difference analysis

Variable	t-test	df	Sig.
Spiritual Attitude	-4.534	198	.000
Cognitive Emotion Regulation strategy	-.881	198	.379

Discussion

The current study investigated the link between spiritual attitudes and cognitive emotion control mechanisms in adults, with an emphasis on gender differences. The results show that female participants had a higher level of spiritual attitude than their male counterparts. This shows that women may have a larger affinity for spiritual ideas and practices, which may influence their emotional and psychological coping strategies. The data's graphic portrayal verified this discrepancy, indicating a persistent trend of increased spiritual participation among females. These findings are consistent with prior studies showing that women are more

spiritually inclined, potentially due to socialisation patterns or a greater emotional receptivity to existential and contemplative experiences.

The results demonstrated that males and females had similar cognitive emotion regulation techniques. Both groups appeared to use similar cognitive strategies when dealing with unpleasant emotions or stressful events. This data implies that gender may not play an important impact in how people cognitively manage their emotions. The consistent usage of methods such as acceptance, reappraisal, and planning across genders suggests that these cognitive processes are widely shared,

independent of spiritual orientation or demographic background.

It was shown that there was a good correlation between spiritual attitude and cognitive emotion management techniques. This indicates that people who had a more spiritual perspective were more likely to manage their emotions with useful cognitive techniques. According to the link, spirituality can be a useful psychological tool that fosters inner fortitude, emotional stability, and stress-resilience. This study suggests that spiritual beliefs may promote more adaptive emotional responses, which is consistent with previous research that highlights the positive role of spirituality in emotional well-being.

Finally, the group differences analysis revealed that there was no difference in cognitive emotion regulation between males and girls, but there was a significant difference in spiritual attitude. This supports the idea that, although spirituality tends to differ between women, emotional regulation skills are largely the same. The study's hypothesis—that there are gender variations in spirituality but not in cognitive or emotional coping mechanisms—is partially supported by this.

Conclusion:

This study discovered that a more spiritual mindset is associated with improved cognitive emotion control techniques. Females had greater spiritual attitudes than males, although both genders used similar emotional regulation strategies. These findings emphasise the

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relevance of spirituality in improving emotional functioning and imply that cultivating spiritual awareness can help young adults' mental well-being.

Research Finding:

- Compared to men, women showed a greater degree of spiritual attitude, suggesting a greater propensity for spiritual behaviours and beliefs.
- The use of cognitive emotion regulation techniques did not significantly differ by gender; both males and females used comparable coping mechanisms.
- Spiritual attitude and cognitive emotion regulation were found to be positively correlated, indicating that people who have greater spiritual beliefs are generally better at controlling their emotions.
- As a personal resource that improves adaptive coping under difficult circumstances, spirituality supports emotional regulation.
- Gender differences exist in spiritual attitude, although cognitive emotion control seems to be a gender-neutral trait.

Research Implication:

- Theoretical: Expands knowledge on spirituality's role in cognitive emotion regulation and rural-urban differences.
- Practical: Guides educators, counselors, and parents in fostering adaptive coping strategies through spirituality.

- Policy: Supports spirituality-based mental health and educational programs tailored to adolescents.
- Future Research: Encourages longitudinal and cross-cultural studies on spirituality and emotional well-being.

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